

AN OVERVIEW LEARNING PROBLEMS (LD STUDENTS) OF SPECIAL EDUCATION PROGRAMS IN MALAYSIA'S COMMUNITY COLLEGE

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Abstract

Learning disabilities students (LD) are the group of children who need special attention. Autism (Autistic Spectrum Disorder), Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and Dyslexia, Dyscalculia and Dysgraphia are included in the group of LD. Community College Management Department (JPKK) is one of the educational institutions in Malaysia that is very concerned on this learning problems. The main purpose of the implementing this program is to give students the skills and knowledge to enable them to adapt to the working environment and to face the real world. A number of programs will be implemented like bakery, culinary, computer, sewing, and photography. Six community colleges were selected to implement the program in their respective colleges. Those colleges are Sungai Siput Community College (KKSS), Bayan Baru Community College (KKBU), Selayang Community College (KKSJ), Jelebu Community College (KKJ), Kuching Community College (KKK) and Paya Besar Community College (KKPB). The number of enrollment per session is 10 students with 3M (reading, writing and arithmetic). The main focus of this study is to review the special education program conducted in all the community colleges under

the supervision of JPKK. The methodology of the study is distributing questionnaires. Data were collected and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 17.0. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of the instrument for lecturers who teaches the LD students is 0.889 and the acceptance of the college citizen is 0.831. This conclude that the skill level of lectures should be improved for them to be more committed and understand the method of teaching and learning of LD students. College infrastructures and curriculum should be revised to provide skills and comfort to the students so they can reap the benefits from this effort. With all these efforts, the JPKK intention to provide knowledge and skills to LD students to become more self-reliant people can be realized.

Keywords: Learning Problems (Learning Disorder), LD program implementation.

Introduction

Malaysia's Special Education program has been devolved under the supervision of the Special Education Department of the Ministry of Education since its formation in October 1995 in the line with the restructuring of the Ministry of Education. The department is professionally responsible for all the implementation of the special education programs in lined with the Integration Special Education Programs and Inclusive Program.

Special Education in Malaysia in the context of the Ministry of Education are implemented in the special schools for visual and hearing impaired students. The Integration Special Education Programs provided students with special needs and learning disabilities, hearing and vision. The program is conducted in the ordinary course in primary and secondary schools. This program include the technical or vocational schools using isolation and semi-inclusive teaching and learning approach.

Facilities for the special education for students with special needs are subject to the Education Act 1996, Regulations of Education (Special Education 1997 Part II 3 (2). The Act clarifies that to be educate a student with special needs is, he or she must be able to take care of themselves without depending on others. They need to be certified by a group of panels consisting of a medical officers, officers from the Ministry of Education and the officers from the Welfare Department. They have to attend a special education program training in accordance with National Education Program to eligible them to be the panels.

Problem Statement

Community colleges were developed in the year 2002. The main purpose of developing community colleges in each state is to help students with to further up their studies especially to the back benches students. The lectures employed to teach in the college are mostly graduates for the varsity. They are equipped with subject matter to teach and they are competent to teach.

When JPKK, starts to implement the Special Education Program - learning disabilities (LD) in the college, in November 2012, most of the lectures find it difficult to conduct the class. Lectures have no background related to the special students and have no prior knowledge in managing special students. The curriculum was built by the lectures with no

background of Special Education Program - LD. From all these scenario researches have been conducted to have an overview in implementing Special Education Program - LD. The researchers would like to identify the suitability of the trainer's skills, the college infrastructure requirements, suitability of the curriculum and the acceptance of every community colleges members towards the Special Education Program - LD

Objectives of The Study

- i. To identify the suitability of the lecture skills in the management of Special Education Students LD in community colleges.
- ii. To identify the infrastructure facilities needed for the Special Education Students - LD in community colleges.
- iii. To identify the appropriateness of the curriculum for the Special Education Students - LD in community colleges.
- iv. To identify the acceptance of the community colleges members towards the Special Education Students - LD in community colleges.

Research Issues

- i. Do the lecturers have the suitable skills in the conducting of Special Education Students - LD in community colleges?
- ii. Does the infrastructure facilities provided for Special Education Students - LD in community colleges suitable?
- iii. Does the curriculum provided suitable of the Special Education Students - LD in community colleges?
- iv. Does the members' community colleges accept the Special Education Students - LD in community colleges?

Research Interests

This study was conducted to determine the extent of conformity implementation and learning opportunities in the community colleges in helping students of Special Education - learning disability (LD). The main purpose is to produce LD students as an individual who is skillful to be able to plan and managing their own lives. To make the LD students realize that they are potential person as an individual and as a member of the society in balanced and having a productive life in harmony align with the National Education Philosophy. In this study, researchers want to look at three main factors to obtain information to empower the Special Education Program in the community colleges.

The results of this study are expected to be benefitted by:

- i. Lectures:
Lectures can design a module and use teaching aids more closely to suit the level of LD students' ability
- ii. Community College:
The college can identify the requirements needed by lectures in conducting the PDP
- iii. Department of Community Colleges:
To let the Department of Community Colleges understand the flow of the Special Education Programs implemented in some community colleges are really up to the standard.

Limitation of Study

This study focuses on the Special Education Programs implemented in the six community colleges. Those six college conducting the special-education students with learning disabilities (LD) are Sungai Siput Community College (KKSS), Bayan Baru Community College (KKBU), and Selayang Community College (KKSJ) where the questionnaires were administered in May 2014. While for Paya Besar Community College (KKPB), Jelebu Community College (KKJ) and Kuching Community College (KKK), the questionnaires was administered in November 2014.

Literature Review

Special Education Program to The Learning Dissabilities

Special education is the education provided to children with special needs. The special needs include those who are visually impaired, hearing problem and learning disabilities and gifted people. Teaching techniques are designed for individuals with special needs to meet the needs related to the education of pupils with disabilities. Special education provides learning opportunities that are not available in the standard or normal curriculum (Calcutta, RA, & Tompkins JR Fundamentals of Special Education, 1999). The Education Act 1996 for special needs students under the supervision and responsibility of the Ministry of Education states that students with special needs is defined as students who have a visual impairment, hearing and learning problems. Children with learning disabilities are defined as students who have cognitive problems which they might be taught (educable) and can benefit from formal education that includes:

- a. Children with Down syndrome
- b. Lightweight Autistic Children
- c. Children with mental ability
- d. Emotionally troubled children
- e. Problem child health
- f. Children's speech and language disorders

The granted conditions to participate in the Special Program conducted by the government or government-aided schools in Malaysia, are children that can be educate, except for those who are physically handicapped, but has the mental capacity to learn, such as normal students with multiple disabilities or who suffers the serious physical handicapped or severe mental retardation (homes / hospitals / under JKM).

The students with special needs are those who can be educate if they are able to take care of themselves without relying on the others and approved by a panel consisting of: medical practitioners, officials from ministry of education and officers of Jabatan Kebajikan Malaysia (JKM) as capable in accordance with the national education program. Special Education students with learning disabilities are categorized as:

- i. Autism
- ii. Down Syndrome
- iii. Cerebral Palsy
- iv. Alexia
- v. Hyperactivity (ADHD) / hypoactive
- vi. Inert

- vii. Gifted Children
- viii. Minimal mental retardation

Each of these students has different potential. Various levels of teaching and learning techniques are applied on these to see the students' abilities. They can be categorized into three sections which are good, average and weak. To meet up with the individual needs of teaching and learning processes, the Special Education Program Integration with Learning Disabilities formed a flexible basis which coincides with the Regulations of Education (Special Education) Act 1997, state that teachers can modify the method or technique of teaching or learning, time for activities and activity structure, subjects and teaching aids to achieve the objectives and goals of Special Education.

Lecturer Presentation Skills on Special Education Students

The knowledge and experience of trainers is the key factor in the process of teaching and learning. Trainers who have the knowledge and skills in special education can produce excellent students. Through the study conducted by Mohd Rizal B. Mohd Said and Muallimah Bt Arshad, from the Faculty of Education UTM found out that trainers really need additional training and workshops to develop themselves. This is because most of the lectures do not have professional qualifications in the special education field and find it difficult to deliver the teaching and learning for these students. The problems related to instructional materials for teaching, special education teachers have had difficulty in building teaching aids, using their own creativity without the help of others. This is because many of these teachers do not have enough exposure to make teaching aids for special education students, as well as the lack of teaching aid provided by other parties. According to Mat Nor Husin (1988), which states that if teaching aids are used in the right way and fits in a teaching situation, this objective can be achieved and provide a stronger foundation and concept that can result in lifelong learning.

Acceptance of Technical Institute Of Higher Education

Among the factors driven in the growth of special education students is the process of acceptance in the educational institution itself to the special education students. In a global program mandates, the United Nations for Disabled (United Nation Global Programmed on Disability) in an article entitled Policy and Implementation of the National Education System by Civil and Syed Othman (2001) suggest three objectives, namely as

- a. People with disabilities should be given the opportunity and encouragement to develop themselves and participate in society effectively.
- b. Rights and dignity of people with disabilities must be protected. This would opened the eyes of society that people with disabilities can also provide a good contribution if they are given the opportunity and appropriate rights.
- c. Express equality opportunity for employment, education, information, goods and equipment, and services.

Facilities Provided For Special Education Students

The college environment should be conducive. This is the most basic requirement for providing optimum learning opportunities for all students including the special education students. Physical facilities such as classrooms, laboratories, culinary lab and other facilities

in college should accommodate the special needs students. According to Gopelajar Idsmith (1998), children with special needs should feel comfortable, safe and controlled when lesson is on sessions.

For the purpose of teaching and learning process to be more effective, the layout of the classrooms need to be different compared to the higher level. Physical atmosphere in the classroom seating arrangement plays a particularly important role. Room size should be appropriate for teaching and learning so that the learning can be performed comfortably. Furniture should be arranged in an effective position to allow the lecturer to move easily around the students.

The educational skills trained in the community college for the special students involves skills such as pastry, culinary, sewing, food processing, information technology and photography. The safety aspect is important for special education students. The college management should always consider and provide classroom located on the basement near to the washrooms.

Curriculum for Special Students

The Special Education Curriculum - Learning Disability (LD) was built accordance to the level of ability and needs. The curriculum for this group students are focused on mastering skills to meet the needs of individuals, and not too stressed on academics. In the first phase, students with Special Education - Learning Disability (LD) will be provided with the 3M foundation that is reading (Membaca), writing (Menulis) and mathematics (Mengira). They also must have the Life Management, Creative Arts, Islamic Studies, Moral and Sports Education. Meanwhile in the second phase, these students are provided with subjects learning such as Malay, English, Mathematics, Islamic Studies, Moral Education, Sports and Health Education, Science, Social and Environment, Visual Arts, Music Education, Basic Life Skills, Information Technology and Communications, and Life Management. Teaching and learning programs for all three categories is also formed in a flexible manner in accordance with the Regulations of Education (Special Education) Act 1997.

Methodology

Study Location

This study focuses on the field of special education programs, LD implemented in six community colleges that are KKSS, KKBU, KKSU, KKJ, KKK and KKPB.

Population and Sample Survey

The study included respondents from special education students, special education lecturers and the college members at six community colleges that offers special education programs. The main focus of researchers is to carry out a review of the implementation of special education programs at community colleges.

Instrument Review

In achieving the objectives of a study it is important to use instrument (Mohd Majid, 2000). The instrument used in this study is questionnaires. Because the study is a survey, a suitable method is to use a questionnaire as an instrument. Refer to Table 1.

Table 1- The Types of Questions

NO	ITEM	NO OF QUESTIONS	SCALE
1	RESPONDENT DEMOGRAPHY	4	
2	QUESTIONS TO LECTURERS TEACHING LD STUDENTS		
A	The lecturers level skills	10	
B	The curriculum level for LD students in Community	10	
C	The infrastructure facilities level in Community College	10	
3	SURVEY QUESTIONS TO RESIDENTS (ONLINE/SURVEY FORM)		
	College members perception	10	

Analysis Method

Two sets of questionnaires were administered. One set of questionnaires to the lecturers who teaches the LD students. This questionnaires are divided into 4 parts those are, Part A – The Demographic of The Lecturers and part B - The Lectures Level of Skills, Part C - The infrastructure facilities level in Community College and Part D -. The Curriculum Level for LD student in Community College Overall the data were analyzed using SPSS 17.0 (Statistical Package for Social Science).

Statements provided in the questionnaires are 5 Likert scale. 5 Likert scale is used in this study because it has a level of reliability and good accuracy of 85% (Mohamad Najib, 1999). Likert scale is appropriate because it is an inventory involving individual feelings toward any idea, procedure and social institutions. The Likert scale use in the study are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 - Likert Scale

LIKERT SCALE	STATEMENT	
1	Strongly Disagree	SD
2	Disagree	D
3	Less Agree	LA
4	Agree	A
5	Strongly Agree	SA

Pilot Study

The questionnaires were built by Nurul Zihar, from UTM in her study of LD students. A pilot study was conducted because the researchers have modified the questionnaires to adopt with the current issue of LD students in college community. The questionnaires were administered to 15 students LD, 7 teachers and 35 college members (teachers and students) from Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Muhibbah, Perak. The pilot study was not only a good practice to fix any errors even useful for the training of future researchers conducting the actual study. (Cooper, 1998). The errors found in the questionnaire will be altered before being distributed to the real situation. The calculation of the reliability coefficient using SPSS Version 17.0 shows that the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient value for the instrument studies on lecturer who teaches LD students is was 0.889. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient value for the citizens of the college in accepting the LD students is 0.831. According to Majid Konting (2000), the coefficient of reliability that is often used is more than 0.70. Therefore, items that are built are in good reliability and can be administered. According to Sekaran

(2003) reliability is a measure for the stability and consistency, where an instrument can measure a concept put forward and assist in assessing the strength of a measuring it. Refer to Table 3.

Table 3 - Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient value.

TAHAP	TAFSIRAN
0.60	Weak
0.70	Applicable
0.80	Good

Data Analysis

Findings and Analysis

The questionnaires were distributed to six colleges, KKBU, KKSJ, KKSS, KKPJ, KKJ and KKG. Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 17.0. Davies (1971) said that low, medium and high, are based on a five-point Likert scale that is being used. In this study, the researchers put into 4 levels, ground, low, medium and high as had been done by previous researchers as Norasmah (2001). The level is based on the mean scores as shown in table 4.0 in the appendix.

Table 4 - Score Level Determination Based on Min

Mean Score	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.99	Weak
2.00 – 2.99	Low
3.00 – 3.99	Average
4.00 – 5.00	High

Analysis Part A - Demographic Data

Table 4.2.1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the lectures gender. The findings showed that the respondents from KKSS consist of 1 man, 25% and four female respondents, 75%. Meanwhile there were two respondents in KKBU, 100%. Whereas in KKSJ, there were two female respondents, 50% and 2 male respondents, 50%. In KKPJ and KKG there were 3 female respondents, 100% and in KKJEL there were 2 female respondents, 100%.

Table 4.2.1- Lecturers Gender Analysis

BIL	ITEM	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS / PERCENTAGE (%)					
		KKSS	KKBU	KKSJ	KKPJ	KKJEL	KKG
1	Male	1 (25%)	0 (0%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
2	Female	4 (75%)	2 (100%)	2 (50%)	3 (100%)	2 (50%)	3(100%)
	Total	5 (100%)	2 (100%)	4 (100%)	3 (100%)	2 (100%)	3 (100%)

Table 4.2.2 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of age trainers. The findings showed that 5 respondents KKSS aged between 26 - 33 years, 100%. While KKBU shows a respondent aged between 26 - 33 years, 50%, and a respondent aged between 34 - 41 years, 50%. For KKSJ, respondents aged between 26 - 33 years are 3 people, 75%, between 34 and 41 years, 50%. While KKPJ, 3 respondents aged 26 - 33 years, 100%, while KKJEL two

respondents aged 26 - 33 years, 100%. As for KKKG, two respondents aged 26 - 33 years, 66.3% and respondents aged 34 - 41 years, 33.33%.

Table 4.2.2 - Lecturers Age Analysis

BIL	PERKARA	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS / PERCENTAGE (%)					
		KKSS	KKBU	KKSY	KKPB	KKJEL	KKKG
1	18 – 25 years old	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	26 – 33 years old	5 (100%)	1 (50%)	3 (75%)	3(100%)	2(100%)	2(66.33%)
3	34 – 41 years old	-	1 (50%)	1 (25%)	-	-	1(33.33%)
4	More than 42 years old	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Total	5 (100%)	2 (100%)	4 (100%)	3(100%)	2 (100%)	3(100%)

Table 4.2.3 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of lecturer's year of service. The findings showed that three KKSS lecturers have 5 years, one lecturer have 10 year old and one lecturer has 6 year old. In KKBU one lecturer have served 11 years and one lecture have 2 year service. Meanwhile in KKSY, there are three lecturers who have served for 3 years and one for 4 years. For KKPB, the years of service respectively 5, 3 and 2 years of service. For KKJEL respondents are respectively 8, 5 and 3 years of service.

Table 4.2.3 - Lectures Year of Service

BIL	ITEM	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS / PERCENTAGE (%)					No of Lecturer
		Lecturer 1	Lecturer 2	Lecturer 3	Lecturer 4	Lecture 5	
1	KKSS	10 years	6 years	5 years	5 years	5 years	5
2	KKBU	2 years	11 years	-	-	-	2
3	KKSY	3 years	3 years	3 years	4 years	-	4
4	KKPB	5 years	2 years	3 years	-	-	3
5	KKJEL	8 years	8 years	-	-	-	2
6	KKKG	3 years	5 months	8 years	-	-	3

Table 4.2.4 shows the frequency distribution and percentage of lectures area of specialization. The findings showed that 3 KKSS lecturers are specializing in IT field, one in the counseling and one in the Islamic Education. While for the respondent in KKBU, there are one lecturer specializes in pastry and one lecturer specializes in computer and Bahasa Melayu. For KKSY, there are two lecturers specialize in culinary, one in special education and sign language. While for KKPB, 2 lecturers who specialize in photography and Fine Art. Both lectures from KKJ are specializing in food processing. Meanwhile in KKKG two lectures are in fashion and one in IT.

Table 4.2.4 - Lecturer Specialization Analysis

NO	ITEM	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS / PERCENTAGE (%)					No of Lecturer
		Lecturer 1	Lecturer 2	Lecturer 3	Lecturer 4	Lecturer 5	
1	KKSS	Counseling	IT	IT	Islamic Education	IT	5
2	KKBU	Pastry	Computers / B.M	-	-	-	2
3	KKSY	Culinary	Sign Language	Culinary	Special Education	-	4
4	KKPB	Photography	Fine Art	Photography	-	-	3
5	KKJEL	Food Processing	Food Processing	-	-	-	2
6	KKKG	Fashion	Fashion	IT	-	-	3

The findings Lectures Skills Level in Community Colleges.

Referring to the suitability skills of lectures in the managing the special education LD shows a mean score for 3:34 for KKSS, 3:05 for KKPU, 4:05 for KKSJ, 3.86 for KKPB, KKJEL with 4:00 and 3:36 for KKKG. This means that the lecturers skills in the managing the special education for KKSS, KKPU, KKPB, and KKKG respectively were average. While KKSJ and KKJ were high. This shows that the lecturer in KKSJ and KKJ were skillful and knowledgeable in special education area.

Table 4.3.1 - The mean score for Level Lectures Skills

ITEM	MEAN SCORE / STANDARD DIVIATION LEVEL					
	KKSS	KKBU	KKSJ	KKPB	KKJEL	KKKG
Scores Mean,	3.34 (Average)	3.05 (Average)	4.05 (High)	3.86 (Average)	4.00 (High)	3.36 (Average)

The Findings of Infrastructure Facilities Level in Community College.

Referring to the second research question, namely the infrastructure facilities provided for special education students most of the mean score for the six colleges involved were at the average level. The mean score for KKSS were 3:08, KKBU and KKSJ both 3:15, KKPB was 3:46, 3:40 for KKJEL and for KKKG 3:36. This means that the infrastructure facilities provided by the college were in moderate and average condition.

Table 4.3.2 - The infrastructure facilities level in Community Colleges

ITEM	MEAN SCORE					
	KKSS	KKBU	KKSJ	KKPB	KKJEL	KKKG
Scores Mean	3.08 (Average)	3.15 (Average)	3.15 (Average)	3.46 (Average)	3.40 (Average)	3.36 (Average)

The Findings of Curriculum for LD Student Level in Community College

Referring to the third question, the applicability of the curriculum provided to special education students shows the mean score for the 4 college KKSJ score 3.67, KKSS were 3.62 3.95 for KKPU and 3.66 KKKG respectively. While for KKPB 4.69 and KKJEL 4.50 respectively. This shows that the curriculum in the college community should be more purified to achieve the JPCK to provide knowledge and skills for students LD.

Table 4.3.3 - The appropriateness curriculum level for LD students in Community Colleges

ITEM	MEAN SCORE					
	KKSS	KKBU	KKSJ	KKPB	KKJEL	KKKG
Scores Mean	3.62 (Average)	3.95 (Average)	3.67 (Average)	4.69 (High)	4.50 (High)	3.66 (Average)

Findings Acceptance Factor Of the College Members towards LD Students in Community Colleges

Referring to the last research question, the acceptance factor of Citizens College towards LD student in community colleges showed higher mean scores for almost the whole colleges involved. The table 4:4 shows the mean score for each community college. The mean score for KKSS was 4.15, KKBU was 4.17, KKSJ is 4.02, KKJEL is 4.11 and the KKKG is 4:28.

Meanwhile KKPB was 3.92. This means that the college members can accept the special education students in the college.

Table 4.4 - The acceptance level of community college citizens towards LD students

ITEM	MEAN SCORE					
	KKSS	KKBU	KKSY	KKPB	KKJEL	KKKG
Scores Mean	4.15 (High)	4.17 (High)	4.02 (High)	3.92 (Average)	4.11 (High)	4.28 (High)

Conclusions And Summary

Based on the overall study, the objective of implementing the special education program LD in community colleges is on the variety level. This is because the data obtained show that there were colleges that reach a mean score of 2.00 which is low level and almost most of the college mean scores in the high level of 4.00 points.

The first objective of this study is the applicability of the Lectures Skills Level in Community Colleges in the management of special education students LD. The lecturers are expert in their respective fields of PDP. However, the study showed that lectures teaching LD students need to be given more courses, exercises and related disclosure rules in PDP of the LD students and methods to manage them. This is to enable them to equip themselves to provide high commitment to produce LD students who knowledge and skills.

Next was to identify the needs of the infrastructure facilities provided special education LD students in community colleges, also showed a moderate level of mean scores. Community College is an institution that provides skills to students. Based on the findings, the overall facilities available in the college was not enough to give comfort to the LD students. This finding was also stated that in the library there is no books that are available as the appropriate reading material for the LD students. When conducting practical's in the lab, LD students need to repeat several times to master the skills but the material or the equipment is not enough for the LD students to repeat the practical all over again. Infrastructure should be improved to ensure LD students PDP can run more efficiently and comfortably.

Suitability factor curriculum provided for the special education students in community colleges showed a moderate level of mean scores. The curriculum was built initially through the existing knowledge of the lecturer in their field regardless of the technique PDP LD students. When the PDP was conducted, it was found that the curriculum is at a relatively high level and less compatible with the intellectual LD students. However, the construction of the curriculum is compatible with the requirements of the industry. This shows that the curriculum built should be enhanced LD student's achievement and provide knowledge and skills to LD students.

The final objective of this study was the acceptance factor of college members towards LD student in community colleges. The finding showed that individuals in all the colleges offering special education indicate a high mean score. This indicates that either the citizen

college can adapt the existence of the LD student in the college teaching and learning system although the students have disabilities.

The conclusion here, it can be said that to manage teaching and learning for LD student, every aspect should be taken into consideration. The lecturers' skills level need to be improved to make them more committed in their teaching and learning towards the LD students. Infrastructure and curriculum need to be adjusted in order to provide comfort to the students for them to acquire LD benefit from this noble effort. With all these efforts, the desire of the JPKK to provide the knowledge and skills to LD students to become more self-reliant human in the real world can be realized.

Further Study Findings And Recommendations

Throughout this study, researchers have found some interesting findings that need an attention. The findings are as follows:

i. Pedagogical knowledge PDP LD students

On the whole, the lecturers who teaches the LD students are competent in their fields. However, the knowledge of teaching techniques (PDP) for the LD students are still at a moderate level where as the lecturers should be given a more in-depth training. This is due to our findings through interviews that were conducted with the lecturers involved.

ii. LD student management skills

Through the interview conducted to the lecturers, most of the lectures said that there were varieties of behavior of the LD students'. This made it more difficult to control and manage them. Experience and skills are needed to manage LD students who have various whims.

iii. Inadequate infrastructure facilities

From the feedback and observations of the lecturers' the researchers found that the facilities and materials of PDP is not sufficient to complete the syllabus that has been built. This is one factor that show that the learning objectives set for LD students are not achieved.

iv. Not all LD students can undertake industrial training beyond college

The results obtained from the lecturer's feedback were there are students who are not accepted by the industry to undergo industrial training. The industry is not confident of their abilities and skills. In fact, they are not willing to deal with the problems that will be incurred by the LD student. Furthermore, the industries itself has no knowledge in the management of LD students.

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